

Data Governance Powers Big Data Analytics

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

In this age of big data and consumer privacy, organizations must adhere to information management practices that comply with requirements involving data privacy, security and governance for customer analytics. But for those that analyze disparate data types—geospatial, machine generated and unstructured—they must develop a strategy that goes beyond mere infrastructure and architecture solutions. In this session, Environics Analytics executive James Smith will discuss practical strategies to implement, manage and measure their data governance, privacy and security programs with ease. Learn from this industry veteran about what works and what doesn't for big data and analytical initiatives.

2. Aim

To provide the audience with an understanding of

- How to implement various DG models
- Data Management Strategies that enable your DG program
- DG Measurement and Value factors
- Self Audit Best Practices

3. Material and methods

Information gathered from 30 years of progressive experience of analyzing data and managing data programs that address the objectives, in a unified, cross-disciplinary way of Privacy, Security and Governance

4. Results

Data Best Practices
Operable DG program
DG Value Model

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5. Conclusions

The programs I have implemented have helped the organization with

- Increased Data Products
- Increased Data Quality
- Being Auditable and Sustainable
- Overall Corporate Awareness
- Less Data Risk

6. Keywords

Data Governance; Data Analytics; Data Strategy; Environics Analytics

Author biography

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